

RESO

WP2-RP03:

Draft Data Model Report

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Executive Summary

This conceptual data model has been created using the energy datasets gathered throughout the RESO project and presented in the RESO data catalogue. Centred on the property as a fundamental geographical entity, the data model shows relations between different tiered-geographies which were of interest to the RESO project. These include postcodes, ONS statistical areas and the electricity network, in addition to the attributes associated with each object such as the annual domestic gas consumption of a postcode, number of cars kept with in an output area (OA) or firm capacity of a primary substation. These attributes can be numerical, text-based or Boolean (i.e., True/False) in form, or in some cases a time-series at a specified granularity (e.g., primary substation monitoring data). The rows of the object's attributes in the data model schematic are colour filled depending on which category of data they fall under (e.g., transport, electricity or socioeconomic) and their codes in the data catalogue (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4776521>) are given for easy cross-referencing between the two documents. Furthermore, unique identifiers have been assigned to objects where they exist to remove any potential ambiguity in naming and improve interoperability.

It is intended for the data model to serve two purposes. Firstly, as a visualisation aid to more easily browse the data landscape that the RESO project has investigated, which could be of use to the project internally as well as of benefit to smart local energy systems projects in other areas. Secondly, it could act as a stepping stone for a machine readable database which could be developed and maintained by a RESO or RESO-like organisation which grows as more data becomes available. Although extensive in detail, it should not be viewed as an exhaustive list of every geographical level or associated attribute and this document should be seen as an accompaniment to the diagram. After an introduction to entity-relationship data models and crow's foot notation, each entity and relationship is presented with a deeper discussion on its meaning or exceptional cases. Finally, the limitations of the data model as it stands are briefly discussed as well as potential next steps to take the human-readable conceptual data model into one that is machine-readable and able to be handled by a single database.

Background

In 2019 the UK was the first developed country to pass a net zero emissions target into law. Being net zero by 2050 underpins the UK's commitment to the UNFCCC COP 21 2016 Paris Agreement to keep global warming under 2°C. However, the cumulative amount of emissions is ultimately the driver of climate change, e.g., it is the amount of CO₂ emissions released on the way to net zero rather than the net zero target itself which is the important factor. Nonetheless, the net zero target by 2050 provides a singular and defined target whereby the UK will no longer be adding to the global total of Green House Gas emissions from a territorial emissions perspective.

The Regional Energy System Operator (RESO) project is a detailed design project funded by Innovate UK from January 2020 to December 2021 with a focus on the decarbonisation of Coventry City Council local authority area. The aim of the RESO project is to create a cleaner, lower cost energy system for Coventry and the West Midlands region that maximises economic opportunities in clean growth and future mobility. Its aim is to help deliver local policy objectives towards the UK's net zero emissions in 2050 framed by the Paris agreement. The timeframe for focus for the RESO project is however 2032, a timeframe when significant decarbonisation must have already taken place within the Coventry City Council local authority area in order to put it on a trajectory appropriate for the UK's 2050 national ambitions.

An aim of the RESO project's detailed design methodology for Coventry is to demonstrate its relevance to the wider region by having an approach for other local authority areas that is repeatable. Within the overall RESO project context of creating a detailed energy system design, the Energy Informatics Group at the University of Birmingham provides input on data foundations with a particular focus on energy data.

Context for Coventry

The city of Coventry is an administrative centre and metropolitan borough in England with an area of 98.64 km². By land use, the local authority is 58% built on, 17% green urban, 25% farmland and <1% attributed to natural area¹. According to the Office for National Statistics (ONS) estimates, the population of Coventry in mid-2018 was about 366,800² with the Gross Value Add per capita standing at £24,890³ (ONS 2017). According to the Local Land and Property Gazetteer there are 145,500 domestic dwellings in Coventry and BEIS 2019 figures state 18.8% of households are in fuel poverty compared to the England average of 13.4%⁴.

The RESO project boundary includes 201 LSOAs. This is made up of the 195 Coventry local authority area LSOAs (green area in Figure 1), and six additional LSOAs Warwick 005G, Rugby (004D, 001C), Nuneaton & Bedworth (015C, 015D, 015E), yellow areas in Figure 1. However, for the energy consumption and carbon emission analysis, these additional LSOAs areas were excluded since BEIS publishes the relevant statistics at a local authority level and the additional LSOA contributions will be small compared to the Coventry local authority area.

Figure 1 - Map of the 201 LSOAs of interest for the RESO area. The 195 Coventry local authority LSOAs are in green and the 6 LSOAs outside the local authority boundary are in yellow.

¹ <https://land.copernicus.eu/pan-european/corine-land-cover>

² <https://www.ons.gov.uk/peoplepopulationandcommunity/populationandmigration/populationestimates/bulletins/annualmidyearpopulationestimates/mid2019>

³ <https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/grossvalueaddedgva/bulletins/regionalgrossvalueaddedbalanceduk/1998to2017#interactive-map-gross-value-added-gva-per-head-for-nuts3-local-areas-1998-to-2017>

⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/sub-regional-fuel-poverty-data-2021>

Introduction to Entity-Relationship Data Models

A data model is a way of organising data to show how the known pieces of information relate to one another under a standardised schema. One widely used type of data model is called the entity-relationship data model due to its relative simplicity and ability to be shown as an interpretable diagram. Entity-relationship models are based on entities, tabular rows that contain the actual data (attributes) for that object, and relationships, how the entities relate to one another⁵. There are three levels of data models: conceptual, logical and physical⁶. A conceptual data model contains just the relations between entities and their generic attributes, while a logical data model sets defined structures for the attributes (e.g., a string or integer of a certain length) and a physical data model is a logical data model that uses unique identifiers for each entity called primary keys. This RESO data model is a hybrid between the conceptual and physical types, since it uses primary keys but does not yet fix the structure for each attribute, so for now shall be referred to as a conceptual data model.

An entity is usually a real-world object (person, building etc.) or tangible concept (course, business etc.) which possesses a set of defining characteristics. Using an example from Tutorials Point for the hypothetical data model of a school, an entity could be a Student with attributes such as First Name, Last Name, Contact Number and Date of Birth⁷. Entities and their attributes can typically either be displayed as a rectangular box for the entity connected by lines to multiple ellipses representing each attribute, or more succinctly in a single table with rows for each attribute. Attributes can take on different forms (variable types) such as numerical (float or integer), text (string) or true/false binary (Boolean). They can also be multivalued (i.e. Contact Number), composite (i.e. Name = First Name and Last Name) or derived (i.e. Age from Date of Birth).

Figure 2 – Example entity and its attributes using elliptical and rectangular notation. Image is a modified version of resources created by Tutorials Point¹⁰.

Another important concept for the creation of a robust data model is ensuring that each entity has an unambiguous unique identifier known as a primary key. Returning to the previous example of a school, it is possible for two or more students to share the same first name and last name. If this situation were to occur, it would be difficult to easily differentiate between the individuals concerned from a data perspective, making day-to-day administrative data tasks much more challenging. Hence, it is common to include another attribute for the entity Student

⁵ <https://opentextbc.ca/dbdesign01/chapter/chapter-8-entity-relationship-model/>

⁶ <https://www.guru99.com/data-modelling-conceptual-logical.html>

⁷ https://www.tutorialspoint.com/dbms/er_diagram_representation.htm

such as a numerical Student ID which is unique for each member. This attribute would serve as the primary key and in the tabular notation, is shown as the first row and underlined in bold.

Student	
PK	<u>Student ID</u>
	First Name
	Last Name
	Contact Number
	Date of Birth

Figure 3 – Example entity and its attributes including a primary key in text box notation.

After outlining the entities and their attributes which make up a data model (for a school, these could include student, class, teacher etc.), it is then necessary to consider the relationships between them. There are essentially three broad types of relationships (with intuitive names) between entities in an entity-relationship model: one-to-one, one-to-many (or its reverse many-to-one) and many-to-many.

Figure 4 – Examples of one-to-one, many-to-one and many-to-many relations between the members (black dots) of entities A and B. Image is a modified version of resources created by Tutorials Point⁸.

⁸ https://www.tutorialspoint.com/dbms/er_model_basic_concepts.htm

Continuing with real situations from the education sector example, the entities student and class could be related either many-to-one (in for example, a primary school where a group of pupils typically have only one class) or many-to-many (such as in a secondary school, where pupils have multiple classes for different subjects). On the other hand, a one-to-one mapping could exist between the entity teacher and class (assuming each teacher teaches only one class).

In more formal data models (such as the one developed for the RESO project), a greater number of relationships can be used to account for whether the relation is optional or mandatory in nature. It is argued by some that all relationships in an entity-relationship data model must be shown as either mandatory or optional, and not to do so is not best practice⁹.

For example, the relationship between the entities Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) and Property can be described as optional since not every property will have an EPC. Whereas, the relationship between the entities Property and Postcode is mandatory since every individual property will be part of a postcode.

There are various notations for displaying relationships between entities, but one commonly used is crow's foot notation. These two ended lines are drawn between the tables of entities and are summarised in the figure below (this notation will be used for the RESO data model).

Figure 5 – Examples of crow's foot notation. Image from Lucid Chart¹⁰

⁹ <https://ics314f13.wordpress.com/modules/model-design/model-design-guidelines/>

¹⁰ <https://www.lucidchart.com/pages/ER-diagram-symbols-and-meaning>

RESO Data Model

The full data model can be viewed in the accompanying pdf created in draw.io¹¹ and the codes for the datasets are those referred to in the RESO data catalogue¹². In this section each entity will be discussed as well as the assumptions and uncertainties that are present within this data model; a table of the relations between all entities is also given in another accompanying pdf for a concise view of all relations between entities.

Property

Property	
PK	UPRN
GEO-003	Latitude/longitude
BUILDINGS-007	Polygon of building footprint
BUILDINGS-007	Height
GEO-003	Domestic or non-domestic?
BUILDINGS-001	Has domestic EPC?
BUILDINGS-001	Has non-domestic EPC?
BUILDINGS-001	Has DEC?
GEO-003	Address (approved, alternative, historic)
GEO-003	Street
GEO-003	Postcode
GEO-003	BLPU classification
BUILDINGS-008	Has off-street parking access?
MULTIVECTOR-017	Has LCT installed?
ELEC-035	Has suitable rooftop for PV?
GAS-HEAT-028	Has gas meter?
GAS-HEAT-028	Rolling AQ gas consumption
	Connected distribution substation
MULTIVECTOR-006	Electricity meter class and consumption
GEO-002	Is owned by council?
WEATHER-CLIMATE-002	Has point source emissions data?
GAS-HEAT-009	Has CHP?
TRANSPORT-007	Has EV charging station?
BUILDINGS-006	Multiple business uses by floor area

Figure 6 – Property entity and its attributes.

The property is in many ways the fundamental unit of the energy data landscape, something which could be seen as a recommendation of the learning from RESO and has been a central theme in previously developed stock models¹³.

The Local Land and Property Gazetteer (LLPG) is the core dataset underpinning a property based energy systems analysis and data model. These gazetteers are geospatial point layers maintained by local authorities containing information (such as address, postcode and building type/usage) on all properties within their area of administration. Each property is given a unique identifier known as a Unique Property Reference Number (UPRN). LLPGs are periodically updated and can be prone to errors (such as typographical errors in postcodes

¹¹ <https://app.diagrams.net/>

¹² <https://zenodo.org/record/4776522>

¹³ <https://journal-buildingscities.org/articles/10.5334/bc.52/>

and addresses). Property level energy and socioeconomic data are only able to be accessed via a secure environment and this raises some ethical considerations should they become more available to various stakeholders. However, since properties form the lowest level of a natural geographic hierarchy, when taking a more aggregated view, the higher level data (from postcode, to OA, to aggregated national data) could be extrapolated down to a property level as an average to gain a potential indicative value for the desired statistic. This may still raise some ethical considerations, but are less likely to be disclosive in terms of property characteristics or data.

It is also worth mentioning the difference between a building and a property; a property being an object which has a UPRN and Basic Land and Property Unit (BLPU) classification indicating a use of either domestic or non-domestic category whereas a building could include an entire block of converted or purpose-built flats each with a different UPRN. A good binary classification of properties is whether they are domestic or non-domestic. A domestic property is felt to be interchangeable with the term 'dwelling' or 'household' and has a residential BLPU classification, whereas a non-domestic property is defined generally as an LLPG object with a commercial BLPU classification (with a handful of exceptions such as commercial classifications existing for cashpoints, telephone boxes and bus shelters¹⁴). There are approximately 150,000 domestic and 10,000 non-domestic properties in the RESO project area. The entity property relates to postcode in a **mandatory many** to **mandatory one** fashion (as all properties will have exactly one postcode).

While properties to postcodes are a mandatory mapping, this is not the case for EPCs and Display Energy Certificates¹⁵ (DECs), special certificates for public sector buildings with floor area > 250 m²; since not all properties will have an EPC or DEC. Therefore, an **optional one** to **optional many** relation was used between property and these three entities (many because one property could have multiple EPCs from different time periods, the most recent being used as part of the RESO analysis).

It is assumed that all properties connect to the electricity network which is a reasonable assumption for an urban area such as Coventry, although OfGem has estimated up to 100,000 UK households (around 1 in 300) may live off the public electricity grid entirely¹⁶. In this data model, properties are related to low voltage (LV) feeders and distribution substations on a **mandatory many** to **mandatory one** basis. This is in reality true for LV feeders as seen from WPD's dataportal2 (notwithstanding larger industrial properties which may have their own dedicated distribution substation) but is not always the physical case for distribution substations. This is because of the meshed topography of the LV network and presence of normally open switches that allows LV feeders to switch from being served by one distribution substation to another when these are closed and other normally closed switches are opened. However, for simplicity and due to the snapshot view of the RESO electrical system geographic analysis, it was assumed that properties map to distribution substations on a snapshot **mandatory many** to **mandatory one** basis.

Roads are also associated with properties on a **mandatory many** to **mandatory one** basis, which seems a logical assumption. However, the same is not true for gas and heat networks which presently serve 82% and 0.06% of Coventry's domestic and non-domestic properties respectively, so these are **optional many** to **optional one** mappings.

¹⁴<https://s3.eu-west-1.amazonaws.com/static.geoplace.co.uk/downloads/GeoPlace-Data-Entry-Conventions-Best-Practice-for-Addresses-V-3.4-2016.pdf>

¹⁵ <https://www.gov.uk/check-energy-performance-public-building>

¹⁶ <https://www.simplyswitch.com/ofgem-seeks-information-households-not-connected-electricity-network/#:~:text=Previous%20estimates%20have%20pegged%20the,in%20remote%20or%20rural%20locations.>

EPCs and DEC

Domestic EPC		Non-domestic EPC		DEC	
PK	LMK KEY	PK	LMK KEY	PK	LMK KEY
	Current and potential energy rating/efficiency		Asset rating and band		Current and previous operational ratings
	Inspection and lodgment date		Property type		Operational rating band
	Property type and built form		Inspection and lodgment date		Property type
	Floor area		Transaction to trigger EPC assessment		Inspection and lodgment date
	Current and potential carbon dioxide emissions		New build and existing stock benchmarks		Floor area
	Current and potential energy intensity		Main and other heating fuel		Carbon dioxide emissions from heating, electricity and renewables
	Current and potential heating, hot water and lighting costs		Renewable sources		Typical and annual energy intensities for electricity and heating fuel
	Energy tariff		Floor area		Main and other heating fuel
	Has mains gas?		Energy intensity		Percentage of electricity from onsite renewables
	Floor level (if flat), total floors and is it the top floor?		Standard, target, typical and building carbon dioxide emissions		Has air conditioning?
	Heating controls		Largest emissions contributor (e.g. heating or air conditioning)		Air conditioning kW rating
	Multi-glazing proportion, type and area		Has air conditioning?		Largest emissions contributor (e.g. heating or air conditioning)
	Number of extensions, heated rooms and habitable rooms		Air conditioning kW rating		Benchmark performance
	Number of open fire places				Building category
	Number of fixed lighting outlets and percent low energy				Occupancy level
	Hot water description and efficiency				
	Floor, roof, windows and walls description and efficiency				
	Main heating and secondary heating system description and efficiency				
	Main heating fuel				
	Has solar PV, solar thermal or wind turbine?				
	Has mechanical ventilation?				
	Height of floor				
	Heat loss corridor and length of corridor (if flat)				
	Build period				
	Transaction to trigger EPC assessment				
	Tenure				

Figure 7 – EPC and DEC entities and their attributes.

Energy Performance Certificates (both domestic and non-domestic) and DEC map to properties on an **optional many to optional one** basis. In the Coventry local authority area there were 123,000 domestic EPCs, 4,900 non-domestic EPCs and 3,600 DEC. When duplicates are removed, approximately 60% of domestic properties and 50% of non-domestic properties were found to have an EPC. In many ways, these were fundamental units of information used for determining the thermal properties of a specific property or a collection of dwellings within a geographic boundary.

The unique identifier of an EPC or DEC is called an LMK KEY. Through private correspondence with Ordnance Survey a list of mappings for the domestic LMK KEYS to the UPRNs of LLPG objects was obtained (improving the matching accuracy previously attempted by string pattern matching addresses and postcodes from 88% to 99.8%).

EPCs have their limitations such as being based on cost not energy and non-domestic EPCs do not include the energy demand for manufacturing processes which are expected to be a large component of the non-domestic energy demand in Coventry.

Postcodes

Postcode		Postcode Sector		Postcode District	
PK	pcds	PK	pcds (without last 2 characters)	PK	pcds (without last 3 characters)
GEO-006	Latitude/longitude of centroid	GEO-005	Polygon of outline	GEO-005	Polygon of outline
GEO-005	Polygon of outline	GAS-HEAT-013	Has district or communal heat network?	TRANSPORT-005	Registered EVs
	Date of introduction and termination	TRANSPORT-020	Number and types of cars or vans kept		
GEO-003	Number of domestic properties				
GEO-003	Number of non-domestic properties				
GAS-HEAT-003	Number of domestic gas meters				
GAS-HEAT-003	Annual domestic gas consumption				
GAS-HEAT-027	Annual total gas consumption				
GAS-HEAT-005	Number of off-gas network properties				
ELEC-015	Number of domestic electricity meters				
ELEC-015	Number of standard and economy 7 meters				
ELEC-016	Number and consumption of pre-payment meters				
ELEC-015	Annual domestic electricity consumption				
SOC-001	Usual resident population				
SOC-013	Consumer classification				

Figure 8 – Postcode geography entities and their attributes.

An average postcode in the UK has 15 properties but this can vary from just 1 to a maximum of 100¹⁷. There are approximately 6,000 different postcodes in the RESO area. There are three different formats for postcodes: pcd7, pcd8 and pcds which could all be a unique identifier¹⁸. Pcd7 and pcd8 fixes the postcode string to a 7 and 8 character length (including whitespace) respectively, explicit examples of each are shown in Table 1. Pcds is the most common format used and so is generally the easiest to work with, thus was chosen as the primary key for the entity postcode in this data model.

pcd7	pcd8	pcds
CV1 1AA	CV1 1AA	CV1 1AA
CV101AA	CV10 1AA	CV10 1AA

Table 1 – Example full CV postcodes written in pcd7, pcd8 and pcds.

It was decided for simplicity for the RESO project to map postcodes to primary substations on a **mandatory many to mandatory one** basis, even though this is not in reality the case due to the WPD primary polygons being based on Voronoi algorithms¹⁹, i.e., an analysis on the distance between distribution substations that is only loosely based on the terrain or urban landscape, rather than the routes of the LV cables themselves. Whereas the postcodes will

¹⁷ <https://ideal-postcodes.co.uk/guides/postcode-facts>

¹⁸ <https://data.nicva.org/dataset/ons-postcode-products>

¹⁹ <https://www.westernpower.co.uk/downloads-view/118177>

have a much greater link to the urban landscape as they are an agglomeration of properties that allow for greater ease of postal delivery.

However, for the RESO purposes of internal data analysis, such as aggregating domestic annual energy consumption to a primary level or modelling future demands, this was deemed to be a satisfactory approach rather than disaggregating postcodes into fractions of postcodes that straddle two or more HV primary substation boundaries.

At a deeper level of geographic analysis (e.g. LV substations) this mapping changes from a many to one, to a **mandatory many to mandatory many** since a postcode can split across more than one nominal LV substation area. Although the so called ‘deep deep dives’ which use these types of mappings (at the moment drawn manually by inspection) to estimate domestic time series consumption from publicly available BEIS and Elexon data have yet to find a clear use case in the design of the RESO outputs.

Postcodes can be mapped to the ONS output areas on a mandatory many to mandatory one basis since they are the unit from which they are built. A lookup table exists between postcodes and OAs/LSOAs/MSOAs/local authorities and is published by the Open Geography Portal²⁰. However, the ONS does note that there are edge cases where if a postcode straddles a ward/parish/local authority then it will be split into two OAs²¹. Although since these instances are rare, for the purposes of the data model a many-to-one relationship was maintained.

As well as full postcodes, some data is given in the geographic area of a partial postcode. These can be either a postal sector (e.g. CV1 1), postal district (CV1) or even postal area (CV) although no datasets were used in the RESO project at that granularity. As is apparent from their clear text-based hierarchical nature, postcodes to postal sectors, postal sectors to postal districts and postal districts to postal areas all follow **mandatory many to mandatory one** relationships.

OAs, LSOAs, MSOAs and Local Authorities

Output Area	
PK	oa11cd
GEO-006	Latitude/longitude of population weighted centroid
GEO-006	Polygon of outline
SOC-001	Number of domestic properties by tenure
SOC-001	Population by age group
TRANSPORT-002	Number of cars or vans kept
SOC-004	Number of properties by social grade
SOC-001	Number of all-student households
SOC-001	Number of properties by central heating type
ELEC-009	Connected primary substation

²⁰ <https://geoportal.statistics.gov.uk/datasets/06938ffe68de49de98709b0c2ea7c21a/about>

²¹ <https://www.ons.gov.uk/methodology/geography/ukgeographies/censusgeography>

Lower Layer Super Output Area	
PK	<u>lsoa11cd</u>
GEO-006	Name of LSOA
GEO-006	Polygon of outline
SOC-005	Number of fuel poor domestic properties
SOC-003	Deprivation indices
SOC-010	Number of employees by sector
SOC-007	Number of benefit claimants
BUILDINGS-002	Number of domestic properties by build period
WEATHER-CLIMATE-004	Air quality parameters
WEATHER-CLIMATE-004	Access to health assets and hazards
ELEC-023	Domestic FIT installations and capacity
ELEC-023	Non-domestic FIT installations and capacity
ELEC-003	Indicative capacity for heat pumps at LV

Middle Layer Super Output Area	
PK	<u>msoa11cd</u>
GEO-006	Name of MSOA
GEO-006	Polygon of outline
GAS-HEAT-002	Non-domestic annual gas consumption
ELEC-014	Non-domestic non-HH metered annual electricity consumption
SOC-011	Number of businesses and workplace units
TRANSPORT-011	Number of commutes by origin/destination and transport method
SOC-006	Annual household incomes
ELEC-009	Connected primary substation

Local Authority	
PK	<u>LA20code</u>
GEO-006	Name of local authority
GEO-006	Polygon of outline
ELEC-014	Non-domestic HH metered annual electricity consumption
GAS-HEAT-025	Number and capacity of RHI installations by technology
GAS-HEAT-011	Number of communal and district heat networks
WEATHER-CLIMATE-001	Annual carbon dioxide emissions
ELEC-019	Renewable electricity annual generation
TRANSPORT-005	Registered EVs
TRANSPORT-001	Road transport annual liquid fuel consumption by vehicle type
MULTIVECTOR-002	Non-road transport annual liquid fuel consumption
MULTIVECTOR-001	Annual coal, manufactured solid fuel and bioenergy consumption
SOC-009	Population projections
ELEC-010	LCT deployment projections
WEATHER-CLIMATE-006	Hourly time series for insolation and air temperature

Figure 9 – OA, LSOA, MSOA and Local Authority entities as well as their attributes.

Output areas are statistical areas for subdividing the UK and presenting findings from the census used by the ONS. As well as census data they are commonly used by BEIS, MHCLG, CDRC and others as a natural area for presenting data. They are updated every 10 years (last in 2011) and will be again for the 2021 census, so care must be taken when comparing data from different time periods.

They follow a hierarchy of output area (OA), lower level super output area (LSOA), middle level super output area (MSOA) and local authority, with each step up being a **mandatory many** to **mandatory one** relationship. As of 2011, there are 181,408 OAs, 34,753 LSOAs and 7,201 MSOAs in England and Wales (Scotland uses a different system). There were also 331 local authorities in England and Wales in 2021²² (excluding the 24 English county councils which are themselves an amalgamation of lower tier local authorities) ranging in population from 2,200 (the Isles of Scilly) to over 1.1 million (Birmingham) with most having 50,000-500,000 residents.

Typically there are around 5 OAs in an LSOA and 5 LSOAs per MSOA but these are not fixed and in some cases it can be more or less. The minimum, maximum, mean and 95% ranges of household and population numbers for OAs, LSOAs and MSOAs according to the criteria set by the ONS are presented in Tables 2 and 3²³.

ONS area	Min. population	Max. population	Mean population	95% in range
OA	100	625	309	171-486
LSOA	1000	3000	1614	1157-2354
MSOA	5000	15000	7787	5443-11579

Table 2 – Criteria, averages and distributions for populations of OAs, LSOAs and MSOAs.

ONS area	Min. households	Max. households	Mean households	95% in range
OA	40	250	129	79-189
LSOA	400	1200	672	473-1000
MSOA	2000	6000	3245	2240-4824

Table 3 - Criteria, averages and distributions for household numbers of OAs, LSOAs and MSOAs.

LSOAs and MSOAs have a logical naming structure as seen in the following examples: LSOA, Coventry 001A and MSOA, Coventry 001. Having the local authority in the name makes for an easier location of the area in a national context, although OAs do not have this attribute.

²² <https://lgiu.org/local-government-facts-and-figures-england/>

²³ <https://www.ons.gov.uk/methodology/geography/ukgeographies/censusgeography>

However, each level does have a unique alphanumeric identifier (called `oa11cd`, `lsoa11cd`, `msoa11cd` and `LAD20code`), so these were used as the primary keys. Local authorities can also change as well in datasets between different years and this happens more frequently than the change in OA/LSOA/MSOA boundaries. For example in 2019, 8 smaller councils in Dorset merged to form two new unitary local authorities and in Northamptonshire in 2021, its 7 smaller councils also merged to create two new local authorities. Therefore, it can be important to keep up-to-date with local authority boundary changes but thankfully because of the many to one relationship between MSOAs and local authorities, any changes will preserve the consistency at lower geographies.

Due to so much public data being presented in an OA/LSOA/MSOA form, it was necessary to derive a mapping for each of these to a primary substation area, so that various characteristics of the electrical network areas could be captured. To do this different methods were used. For OAs, their population-weighted centroids were used (like with postcodes) to produce a **mandatory many to mandatory one** relationship. The accuracy of this is reasonable due to OAs small size (there will typically be dozens in a primary substation area) but the boundaries do not always overlap cleanly, so this source of uncertainty should be noted.

For LSOAs, their larger size means a many to one relationship is not preferable. Hence, a **mandatory many to mandatory many** relationship is proposed instead. This can be done either manually through visual inspection or could potentially be automated in QGIS to increase its reliability and tractability (through taking an algorithm which badges the LSOA polygon to one or more primary polygons based either simply on the ones any part of it touches or more, in a more nuanced way, with additional information the percentage of its total area in each).

The Energy Systems Catapult independently have provided a list of LSOA to primary substation areas as these two geographical units formed a key part of their Local Energy Asset Representation (LEAR) analysis (although their primary substation areas were different to the ones made available by WPD in GIS form and hence used by the RESO project).

Finally, for MSOAs and primary substation areas another **mandatory many to mandatory many** relationship was introduced. This was easier to derive by manual visual inspection than the LSOA to primary relations due to their larger size (the city of Coventry has 42 MSOAs but 195 LSOAs). Where an LSOA is split between two or more primaries, its associated statistics can also be split proportionately between them, either simply evenly between the primaries concerned (50%-50% for two primaries, 33%-33%-33% for three primaries) or proportionately according to some variable (such as area enclosed by the LSOA in each primary, numbers of buildings, and especially for non-domestic energy consumption employees or floor areas). There is clearly a potential for misallocation errors through this; for example, if the annual non-domestic gas consumption is distributed in a highly non-uniform way across an MSOA but is split evenly across two primaries then the real situation, of annual non-domestic gas consumption for a primary substation area, is not precisely reflected. However, in the absence of more granular data, this was considered a satisfactory approach for the RESO project to allow further analysis to proceed.

Great Britain or United Kingdom

Great Britain or United Kingdom	
PK	
MULTIVECTOR-003	Domestic annual fuel consumption by end use
MULTIVECTOR-003	Non-domestic annual fuel consumption by sector and end use
MULTIVECTOR-005	Annual energy intensities by sector
MULTIVECTOR-005	Annual domestic energy consumption by housing type
MULTIVECTOR-015	Projected annual energy demands by fuel
GAS-HEAT-020	Typical energy savings from retrofit
ELEC-029	Half-hourly electricity generation by fuel source and demand
ELEC-024	Typical half-hourly profiles for each electricity meter class
MULTIVECTOR-018	Anonymized smart meter half-hourly electricity and gas profiles
	Half-hourly gas demand for transmission and all distribution zones
	Gas and electricity network losses
ELEC-026	Electricity day ahead half-hourly prices
ELEC-025	Electricity imbalance half-hourly prices
MULTIVECTOR-008	Consumer satisfaction and prices for electricity and gas supply
SOC-015	Consumer willingness to adopt LCTs
TRANSPORT-014	National travel survey
GAS-HEAT-026	Aggregated half-hourly heat pump demand profiles
TRANSPORT-021	Aggregated half-hourly EV demand profiles
	Annual non-carbon dioxide greenhouse gas emissions

Figure 10 – Great Britain or United Kingdom entity and its attributes.

National level data was extrapolated down to be used in the RESO project area. Some examples include the apportionment of the end uses of energy vectors in different sectors in the Sankey diagram methodology, the use Elexon time series profiles to estimate domestic electricity demand and aggregated after diversity heat pump/EV half-hourly demands from nationwide studies. As the local authorities all map to the country in a **mandatory many to mandatory one** basis, it can be shown on the entity-relationship diagram.

LV Feeder

LV feeder	
PK	
BUILDINGS-007	Estimated cable routes
ELEC-007	Real cable routes
	Current limit

Figure 11 – LV feeder entity and its attributes.

Low voltage feeders are the cables located on streets (typically underground) that operate at 400 V and supply power from distribution substations to the meters of properties (on a **mandatory one** to **mandatory many** basis). In their LEAR report²⁴ the Energy Systems Catapult estimate there to be 1200 km of LV feeders in the RESO area and Wattify state a single LV feeder typically powers 30-50 properties with a current rating of 500 A or capacity of 350 kVA²⁵. Neglecting the switches and mesh nature of the LV network, they also nominally relate on a **mandatory many** to **mandatory one** basis with distribution substations, typically 4 LV feeders per distribution substation but sometimes as few as 3 or as many as 10.

In terms of GIS data for the location of LV routes to allow greater precision in property mappings, this is something the RESO project has struggled to obtain. WPD's Dataportal2 platform has been made available which does show the LV cable routes on an interactive map but this is not downloadable as a vector layer for further analysis in GIS software. Although, a higher level geographical analysis may well be sufficient for the scope of this stage of RESO's final outputs. Also since there is no downloadable object to represent each LV feeder, they cannot be given a primary key.

²⁴ <https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/e5qyg/coventry-lear>

²⁵ RESO Deep Dive: Domestic Electric Heat (link not publicly available)

Distribution Substation

Distribution Substation	
PK	<u>Distribution substation asset number</u>
ELEC-001	Substation name
ELEC-007	Latitude/longitude
ELEC-007	Polygon of service area
ELEC-001	Voltage (before/after transformer)
ELEC-001	Asset type
ELEC-001	Firm capacity
ELEC-001	Customer count
ELEC-003	Indicative capacity for EV charging at LV
	Has LV monitoring? (default = no)

Figure 12 – Distribution substation entity and its attributes.

Distribution substations contain transformers that convert the higher voltages of their input feeders (11 or 6.6 kV) into lower voltage 3-phase supplier suitable for commercial/industrial connections or single phase 220V connections to households. There are around 1,700 distribution substations in the Coventry area serving either a single large power consuming industrial site, several non-domestic medium power users or hundreds of domestic properties and small non-domestic premises with transformer ratings ranging from 25 to 1000 kVA.

Unlike the LV feeders, the co-ordinates of each distribution substation are available either in the csv provided by WPD²⁶ or as a download from Dataportal2, so these can be imported as a point layer into GIS for further analysis. The same Voronoi analysis as used by WPD to derive their primary substation area polygons can then be replicated.

The distribution substations also have unique 6-digit numerical asset numbers which can serve as a primary key; this is better than the name (usually the street or organisation it is located) which may be non-unique or even be different string descriptive names between the two datasets (WPD csv and Dataportal2 download).

Distribution substations were said to be mapped to LV feeders and properties via a **mandatory one** to **mandatory many** relationship. Moving up the voltage levels, in this data model distribution substations are related to high voltage (HV) feeders on a **mandatory many** to **mandatory one** basis. This is justifiable from the data available but is subject to change as different distribution substations are 'linked' to an HV primary substation. Indeed, there is a minor difference between WPD provided datasets from a csv and the connected data file that are both snapshots of the network assets connections at that time.

Though each distribution substation is likely to remain associated with only one HV feeder, the mesh nature of the HV (as well as LV) network means that they can change from time to time (i.e. during periods of maintenance or due to network realignment). The operational timeseries data from WPD showed this happening, where parts of the network were de-energised, and the electrical flow routed through another part of the network.

²⁶https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/e73qj/extended-csv-wpd-distribution-substations-coventry-reso_wpd_csv_05_v1

HV Feeder

HV Feeder	
PK	<u>HV feeder asset number</u>
ELEC-007	Lines of cable route
ELEC-007	Polygon of service area
ELEC-007	Conductor material
ELEC-001	Voltage
ELEC-007	Underground or overhead?
	Current limit and implied firm capacity
ELEC-002	Half-hourly monitoring data

Figure 13 – HV feeder entity and its attributes.

HV feeders connect primary substations to distribution substations and operate at 11 kV or 6.6 kV. These conductors can carry up to 300 A of current (or around 6 MVA or 3 MVA of apparent power depending on the voltage) and the Energy Systems Catapult calculated there to be 750 km of HV feeders in the RESO area. The HV feeders map to primary substations on a **mandatory many** to **mandatory one** basis (typically 8-16 feeders per primary) and distribution substations in a **mandatory one** to **mandatory many** relation (usually 5-20 distribution substations per HV feeder). Distribution substations may be able to switch onto other HV feeders due to the mesh nature of the network by changing normally open points to closed (and vice versa), whereas the HV feeders themselves are intrinsically linked to the primary substation. HV feeders also have a unique numerical identifier, 6 digits followed by a forward slash and 4 more digits to serve as the primary key.

The lines of the HV feeders could be downloaded as a vector layer for GIS from Dataportal2. However, these lines in themselves cannot create a clear geographical boundary for the area served by that circuit, but the distribution substation Voronoi-derived polygons can be stitched together under a common badged HV feeder, to obtain a shapefile for the area served.

Finally, it is worth noting in terms of the RESO project and WPD's practices in the Coventry area that HV feeders are the lowest voltage level of the electricity network with half-hourly monitoring data. Although the data has not been cleaned as of June 2021 because there hasn't been a clear use case and the natural geographic unit for informing RESO design has been the next level up (primary substation).

Primary Substation

Primary Substation	
PK	Primary substation asset number
ELEC-004	Substation name
ELEC-004	Latitude/longitude
ELEC-009	Polygon of service area
	Voltage (before/after transformer)
ELEC-004	Firm capacity, peak demand and demand headroom
ELEC-004	Fault current
ELEC-004	Reverse power capability and generation headroom
ELEC-008	Connected generation and total inferred generation
ELEC-032	Half-hourly monitoring data
ELEC-010	LCT deployment projections
ELEC-010	Domestic and non-domestic new development projections

Figure 14 – Primary substation entity and its attributes.

Primary substations are the assets which transform the voltages of the EHV network down (33 kV) to those used in HV feeders (11 or 6.6 kV) connecting to distribution substations. There are 25 primary substations in the RESO project area with firm power capacities ranging from 6-40 MVA (the majority in the range 20-24 MVA). Primary substations typically serve 1,000 to 10,000 domestic properties and hundreds of non-domestic consumers. The primary substations have a unique 6-digit numerical code which is conveniently the same first 6 digits as the HV feeders' asset number (if that feeder is on the same primary). This means they have a primary key and a clear way of mapping to downstream infrastructure objects. They map to HV feeders in a **mandatory one to mandatory many** and the EHV feeders on a **mandatory many to mandatory one** basis.

The RESO project has been privileged to obtain primary substation half-hourly operational monitoring data for the 25 primary substations over the period July 2017-February 2020. This data has been cleaned by the University of Birmingham and used to inform RESO design²⁷. The character of different substations can be observed by comparing their demand profiles on a weekly basis.

Given this rich source of detailed operational data, the primary substation became a default boundary geography from which to analyse the RESO area and datasets from various other boundaries (LSOA or MSOA). Other data was therefore transposed to primary substation level to gain deeper insight into the characteristics of these geographical areas. This is a key piece of learning from the RESO project, which is further amplified by the demand/generation headroom of substations being a limiting factor on their ability to transition areas to greater levels of electrical low carbon technologies.

Finally, it is worth noting there are two additional primary substations which are neglected from the analysis: Whitley South IDNO and Jaguar Land Rover Whitely. These are non-WPD connections at 33 kV, so the data was not available, although they can be assumed to be a small part of the overall electrical demand of the city (especially since the large commercial buildings in Whitely South are currently in the stage of development and the Jaguar site at Whitely also has connections to the WPD network under Whitely primary).

²⁷<https://data.es.catapult.org.uk/dataset/2zg7p/wpd-halfhourly-mva-data-for-coventry-reso-project-area-primary-substations-cleaned>

EHV Network

EHV Electricity Network	
PK	
ELEC-004	Substation names and asset numbers
ELEC-007	Latitude/longitude
ELEC-009	Polygons of service areas
ELEC-007	Lines of EHV distribution network
ELEC-033	Lines of national grid transmission network
	Voltages
ELEC-004	Firm capacities, peak demands and headroom
ELEC-002	Half-hourly monitoring data
ELEC-017	Location and capacity of power stations
MULTIVECTOR-015	Projected electricity generation and demand
ELEC-006	Planned investment / upgrades

Figure 15 – EHV Electricity Network entity and its attributes.

The extra high voltage (EHV) network consists of all assets operating at 33 kV and above. These include bulk supply points (BSPs) that reduce voltage from 132 kV to 33 kV of which there are 5 in the RESO area, grid supply points (GSPs) that reduce voltage from 400 kV or 275 kV to 132 kV (2 in the RESO area and are the highest level of the network operated by regional distribution companies like WPD as opposed to the National Grid) and the EHV feeders (operating at 132 kV and 33 kV) that transfer power between these points.

Although some monitoring data was provided for the BSPs, it was of little immediate use to the RESO project as constraint at the primary level was the main scope of the RESO analyses. Some of the objects will have unique identifiers although because they did not form an extensive part of the RESO design and were grouped together with non-similar assets from higher voltage levels, in this data model no primary key was used for this entity. Although a generic mandatory one to mandatory many relationship between this part of the network and primary substations is imposed. However, in reality, sometimes the mesh nature apparent and lower voltages can also occur as is apparent from observing EHV cable routes on Dataportal2.

Road Network

Road Network	
PK	USRN
BUILDINGS-007	Lines of roads
GEO-003	Street
GEO-003	Postcode(s)
TRANSPORT-003	Traffic point counts
TRANSPORT-018	Routing information
TRANSPORT-007	EV charging points
	Has on street parking?
	Public transport links
	Cycle lanes / routes
BUILDINGS-007	Estimated LV cable routes

Figure 16 – Road Network entity and its attributes.

The road network includes all the streets of the RESO area which are recorded in the LLPG and are available as geospatial data in the OS MasterMap Topography layer. These range from pathways, cul-de-sacs, thoroughfares and major roads such as A roads and motorways. For unique identifiers, a proposed code is the unique street reference number (USRN), which is an attribute for street records in the LLPG.

The road network can be a useful object for comparing its location with that of the energy distribution networks of different vectors (electricity, gas and heat) as the layout of these will often closely follow the road layout in urban areas; the Energy Systems Catapult have used this approach in their LEAR methodology. In addition, it can be combined with traffic flow data or other datasets such as on-street parking restrictions, public transport routes and cycle paths. These latter 3 pieces of information have not been obtained by RESO in a GIS compatible form yet, so does not feature in the data catalogue.

Gas Network

Gas Network	
PK	
GAS-HEAT-004	Implied half-hourly monitoring data
	Peak demand
GAS-HEAT-029	Lines of LDZ pipe route
GAS-HEAT-024	Lines of NTS pipe route
GAS-HEAT-022	Potential hydrogen repurposing?
GAS-HEAT-008	Has biogas injection?

Figure 17 – Gas Network entity and its attributes.

The gas network is made up gas pipes to carry the natural gas that provides energy for space heating, hot water, cooking and industrial processes. Analogous to how the electricity network operates at different voltages, the gas system uses descending pressures to transport gas from coastal terminals to consumers. There are four general levels of pressure: the national transmission system (NTS) at up to 94 bar²⁸, high pressure to intermediate pressure (HP-IP) at 70 to 2 bar, intermediate pressure to medium pressure (IP- MP) at 2 bar to 75 mbar low

²⁸ <https://www.nationalgrid.com/sites/default/files/documents/35829-TPC%20v4.0.pdf>

pressure (LP) below 75 mbar²⁹. The highest pressure part of the network is owned and operated by National Grid Gas with the distribution networks owned and operated by Gas Distribution Networks.

The relationship between the gas network LP pipes and properties is **optional many** to **optional many** as it known that not every property will have a gas connection; it is estimated from the preliminary design that of the 151,000 domestic properties in the RESO area 27,000 are off the gas grid (18%).

Hourly monitoring data was made available to the RESO project from Cadent but only at a West Midlands level (so was extrapolated down to Coventry based on renormalizing to the annual consumption) and property level monthly usage data was accessible through a platform being developed by Corella, a subsidiary of Xoserve (although RESO is still in an exploratory phase of determining the best way to use this source of data).

Finally, since a substation lowers voltages, the analogous asset in the gas sector would be a conversion point from a higher pressure into a lower pressure tier (known as a governor). Further analysis could therefore, look to draw parallels between the concepts of a primary substation area and region served by the same governor but these are unlikely to overlap well.

²⁹https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/566152/climate-adrep-national-grid-gas.pdf

Heat Network

District Heat Network	
PK	
GAS-HEAT-015	Properties connected
	Polygon of service area
	Lines of pipe route
GAS-HEAT-015	Hourly monitoring data (heat generation / supply)
GAS-HEAT-015	Hourly monitoring data (electricity consumption)
GAS-HEAT-015	Hourly monitoring data (carbon dioxide emissions)
ELEC-031	EfW plant half-hourly generation data
ELEC-031	EfW plant KPIs
GAS-HEAT-016	Potential future expansion?

Figure 18 – District Heat Network entity and its attributes.

Heat networks are a series of pipes that supply hot water or steam that carries heat to buildings rather than through an energy vector such as natural gas or electricity. Heat networks have various different typologies but most require a central unit (or energy centre) to generate heat from the combustion of a fuel (natural gas/biomass/waste/hydrogen) or large heat pump (water/ground/air sourced). This means that an energy centre can either generate (if a CHP) or consume a significant amount of electricity, but they will all consume a significant amount of energy.

In Coventry, the Heatline project utilises waste heat from the energy from waste plant and serves 6 large building complexes in the City Centre providing 8 GWh of heat annually. In the RESO CFES scenarios, a common assumption is the expansion of the Heatline network in the future as well as the construction of new district heating schemes. The entity of the heat network relates to properties on an **optional one to optional many** basis (clearly at a much lower frequency than for the gas network).

There are no publicly available geospatial datasets provided for the routes of pipes (although this may become available in the future) but hourly monitoring data has been provided by Engie for the total heat generated and the amount supplied to each site. Furthermore, no unique identifiers are present, but from new datasets there could be either asset codes for the pipelines or heat supply meters themselves.

Future Opportunities to Build on the Data Model

Each entity has been presented and some relationships described in this document and accompanying diagram. Although there is a focus on the RESO area, most of the datasets are either public or would be available for other geographical areas in other parts of the England and Wales. Therefore, it serves as accompanying information to the data catalogue, for any organisation seeking to undertake similar analysis of local energy assets and datasets in their area.

Future activities to build on this hybrid conceptual data model could be: (i) to fill in the data gaps, either with data that exists and is not able to be shared or data that does not exist but could be collected, (ii) upgrade this hybrid conceptual RESO data model from a human readable diagram into a machine readable database and (iii) the incorporation of other geographical boundaries and entities into the model.

Addressing the first of these issues, the following existing data could potentially be harnessed at a local level:

- Smart meter data (notwithstanding strict data protection concerns)
- Consumption from specific large industrial consumers
- Existing heat network and proposed heat network shapefiles
- Tenure (potentially known from council tax records)
- On-street parking restrictions and cycle lanes (potentially be known by council)
- Public transport routes (presumably held by bus operators)
- Car ownership at property level (presumably held by the DVLA)
- Costs paid by consumers (presumably held by the energy suppliers)
- Electricity network mesh relations (potentially in the Common Information Model, but not used by RESO because a network model was not required)³⁰
- Granular electricity annual consumption at the meter level (technically in UOBDC-MULTIVECTOR-006 but an application to access this has not been made by RESO)
- Fuse limits and phase of MPANs linked to UPRNs (potentially known by WPD)

Moreover, these pieces of information could theoretically be collected:

- LV electricity network monitoring data
- LV electricity network shapefiles and precise substation to property mappings
- MP and/or LP gas network monitoring data
- Independent costings for the upgrading of electricity and gas network assets

³⁰ <https://www.westernpower.co.uk/our-network/energy-data-hub/common-information-model>

- Geographically granular data on appliance ownership
- EPCs for buildings which don't have EPCs
- Energy demand for non-heating/lighting use, especially in the non-domestic sector
- Asset registers for low carbon / smart technologies not covered by the MCS (such as home batteries or EVs)
- Socioeconomic data and consumer attitudes at the household level

These lists are not exhaustive, and will be expanded upon further in a future deliverable for release in late 2021.

Secondly, the data model could be used to develop a database containing this information in a one-stop-shop, user focussed portal. The creation of such a portal would require additional effort than that remaining in the RESO project, but is thought to be an approach that could be of value to the various stakeholders. Rather than spending time to manually find and download different datasets from different sources and deal with the inconsistencies (for example in timestamps, identifiers or geographical boundaries), the portal could more seamlessly display the information requested by a user in more linked and interoperable fashion.

The Erwin data modeller software³¹ has been considered as a means of formalising the diagram created so far with draw.io and setting criteria for the format of each attribute. With the ability for reverse and forward engineering, it could potentially create the database code (in SQL) to underpin such a collection. A similarly useful resource could be the idea of data packages in csv or json format using a shared schema, which is promoted by Frictionless Data³². It is also important to communicate and collaborate where possible with others aiming to achieve similar outcomes, in order to share best practices. Examples include Icebreaker One's Open Energy service (in particular their proposed use case)³³ and making sure to align with previous recommendations of the Energy Data Taskforce and actively feed into future proposals³⁴.

Finally, extra geographical boundaries could be incorporated as entities into a data model. These could include political boundaries such as parliamentary constituencies, council wards or parishes, which are sometimes important to consider for the elected policy makers who will ultimately be influencing the energy related decisions that affect their area. Perhaps as a final thought, the merits of a property centred vs people centred data model should be contemplated. Although buildings are intrinsically linked to the energy demand of a geographical area, it is ultimately the human beings who inhabit, visit or work in those structures that create the requirement for energy to be consumed. Albeit there would be issues around consent for such an organisation to hold explicitly personal data, it could be beneficial to eventually consider people as the fundamental entity in the energy system to gain a deeper insight into their energy requirements, expectations and willingness to engage in decarbonisation. Such an immense personal data collection exercise already exists in the decennial ONS census, so maybe there could be consideration of an individual-focused energy census within a similar legal framework.

³¹ <https://www.erwin.com/products/erwin-data-modeler/>

³² <https://frictionlessdata.io/standards/#standards-toolkit>

³³ <https://energydata.org.uk/phase-2-use-case/>

³⁴ <https://es.catapult.org.uk/case-studies/energy-data-taskforce/>